

Team Based Learning for enhanced engagement in larger class settings: Experiences of business school staff and students

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Abstract

In order to enhance student engagement, Team Based Learning (TBL) (Sweet & Michaelsen, 2012) was adopted by a group of four business lecturers at an Irish third-level institute. TBL (a student centred, team-based pedagogical approach) was a new departure for both lecturers and students. Survey findings indicated that students (N=94) were generally positive about the impact of TBL on their learning. Focus groups with students (N = 6) and lecturers (N=3) identified how the quizzing component of TBL was seen by students as a key driver of engagement with content and with peers. Overall, the in-class engagement levels in large classes were observed by lecturers as being transformed positively. The authors conclude by sharing reflections about challenges of facilitating TBL in larger classes. The need for a technological solution for quick sensemaking of data from students is seen as paramount, along with strong facilitation skills.

Keywords: *Large classes; Team Based Learning; flipped classroom; student engagement; diversity*

1. Description of Teaching and Learning Context

Concerns for student engagement and intercultural integration prompted several lecturers within the Faculty of Business and Hospitality to adopt the TBL approach (Sweet & Michaelsen, 2012) during the 2017/2018 academic year. Lecturers had noted that student engagement with content prior to class was often lacking and that attendance could be improved (particularly in larger class cohorts). Peer-to-peer engagement during class, as well as student-to-lecturer engagement were also areas that faculty felt needed to be enhanced during class time to encourage higher-order learning outcomes within their modules. Finally, lecturers felt that the large lecture setting was also contributing to a lack of integration between local and international students. TBL was adopted within 4 different modules by 4 different lecturers: The modules in which TBL was used were: Organisational Management (N=60 students); Auditing (N=70) Sales Management (N=21); and Management (N = 13).

A full, step by step, outline of what is involved in the Team Based Learning approach is beyond the scope of this article (see Parmalee et al., 2012 for a detailed account). In summary, TBL involves small teams of students working together for the duration of a module. Regular (assessed) individual and team quizzes are conducted in class to encourage student engagement with content (e.g. readings, videos) prior to lectures. Based on the quiz scores, lecturers can identify areas where students may require further clarification and scaffolding.

A mini-lecture tailored to the areas where students may need guidance then takes place. Following on from this, within their teams, students apply their learning to work on pre-prepared problems (e.g. relating to case studies) that they are required to solve together. Teams indicate their solutions to the problems simultaneously in class. The role of the lecturer at this point is to facilitate whole-class discussion (with the lecturer and between teams) in relation to solutions identified by teams. This process of pre-class preparation, quizzing, mini lecturing, group problem solving and whole class discussion is repeated for different sections of the module.

Lecturers viewed this process as being feasible for both small and larger class cohorts as it encouraged active learning, and personal development but did not require the use of extra lecturing or tutoring staff.

2. Literature Review

The impact of increased class size on the learning experiences of higher education students has been articulated by several authors. Increases in lecture class-size are associated with a reduction in quantity and quality of student-teacher interaction, poorer levels of student

engagement with material, less student commitment to courses and lower levels of student motivation and participation in class (e.g. Biggs, 1999; Carbone & Greenberg, 1998; Ward and Jenkins, 1992). Larger class sizes have been hypothesised to increase students' sense of anonymity (Michaelsen & Sweet, 2012) and can encourage instructors to adopt a transmissive approach in their teaching.

The exposition of material in the form of a lecture can be effective in the right context, but can result in limited success when overused or used inappropriately (Good & Brophy, 2003). The evidence suggests that when higher-order learning outcomes are targeted, then more active learning methods can be beneficial. McKeachie et al.'s (1986) review of 17 studies comparing lectures and "discussion" methods of teaching found no significant differences between the two modes in terms of memorisation of factual content. Lectures were, however, found to be less effective for long-term retention of knowledge, transfer of learning to new contexts, development of higher-order thinking and student motivation. Freeman et al.'s (2014) meta-analysis of 225 studies found that active learning in undergraduate science, technology, engineering, and math (STEM) programs improved examination performance by 6% with students in lecture-based courses being 1.5 times more likely to fail. Such findings suggest that teaching innovations that can stimulate active learning can be of great benefit to students who can find themselves in larger class sizes during their higher education experience. TBL is one such innovation, developed to address the need for active learning in larger classes.

TBL is used when instructors seek to nurture higher-order learning outcomes when teaching as opposed to the relay of information (Parmelee et al., 2012). Larry Michaelsen, (credited as the founder of the TBL approach; Balan et al., 2015) discusses how the challenge of ensuring student engagement within a larger class of 120 undergraduate business students (in 1979) was the initial impetus for a series of adaptations to his teaching approach (Sweet & Michaelsen, 2012). Michaelsen's experimentation with his teaching resulted in the TBL approach that is now adopted by instructors from many disciplines throughout the world (Haidet et al., 2014). Allen et al.'s (2013) survey of pharmacy faculty who use TBL in the United States found that 70% of respondents had used TBL for classes of over 100 students. Kibble et al. (2016) and Rajalingham et al. (2018) also present in-depth case studies of using TBL in classes of over 100 students.

Recent meta-analyses show support for the use of TBL in the third-level classroom. Liu and Beaujean's (2017, p. 1) meta-analysis of 38 studies that compared TBL with other methods found it was related to 'a little less than .5 of a standard deviation better academic outcomes than results from comparison pedagogical methods'. Swanson et al.'s (2017) meta-analysis found a moderate positive effect of TBL on content knowledge when compared to non-TBL comparison groups. Such findings support the use of TBL in large class settings.

3. Findings

In order to explore student engagement within modules that used TBL, a survey was designed to ascertain how students perceived TBL to impact their learning, their behaviour and the behaviours of others in the class. 94 of the students who took part in TBL across the 4 modules completed the survey upon conclusion of the module – a 59% response rate. In order to further explore how TBL can impact engagement 6 students and 3 lecturers participated in two separate focus groups facilitated by members of the Learning and Teaching unit.

The findings from the survey indicated that there was significant engagement when the TBL approach was adopted. 67% of students agreed or strongly agreed that “*team members contributed as much as me*” indicating that there were efforts made to work with each other in class. Students valued the discursive elements of TBL indicating that their attempts to achieve the stated learning outcomes of the course were helped by discussions that they had with both their team mates (70% agreed or strongly agreed that their learning was helped by this), and with the lecturer (79% agreed or strongly agreed that their learning was helped by this). Although self-reported, the findings suggest that the students felt that the conversations stimulated through the TBL course design were useful for their understanding of the content.

Qualitative data from questionnaires and focus groups help to illustrate how student engagement was impacted. Positive peer pressure and the regular assessments were deemed to encourage students to be more self-regulated, preparing for class sessions by proactively engaging with pre class content. Attendance was also noticeably impacted.

‘Knowing that my performance can affect the grades of others, motivated me to study more so I don't let them down’ (student)

‘Team-based learning is way more efficient for me...at least every week then I'll try to study the stuff’ (student)

‘Linking the assessment generated considerable interest, certainly it helped from an attendance point of view’ (lecturer)

‘The increase in peer-to peer, and student-to-lecturer engagement was clear to all lecturers involved...[TBL prompted] discussion that you wouldn't get or you wouldn't hear normally in a classroom very often; particularly with a large group and particularly with students who are from different nationalities who might be less confident in group discussion’ (lecturer)

‘There was an awful lot more energy and engagement, we were in it together as opposed to me and them and so that was really good’ (lecturer)

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'I think that team-based learning really increases the amount of communication, so yes I think that's good for interaction between students and lecturers' (student)

3. Implications

In comparison to the traditional lecture, TBL sessions generate high levels of student engagement in terms of peer to peer discussion. Students are 'warmed up' by the team quizzes and a wider range of students can engage in class wide discussions. In larger classes, there can be a lot more contributions than one can encounter in the traditional lecture format. This can challenge the skills of lecturers, and so effective facilitation skills are required in order to provoke debate and discussion in a manner that is encouraging, respectful and impactful.

The quizzing elements of TBL can be administered in various different ways. These range from the use of 'self-assessment scratch cards' e.g. IF-AT scratch cards (Epstein Education, 2019) to more technological solutions e.g. classroom response systems (Sibley & Ostaficuk, 2014). TBL requires the lecturer to gauge data from quizzes 'on the fly' in the classroom. Making sense of quiz scores can become difficult and time consuming with larger cohorts. When there are larger classes the use of a classroom response system does become necessary. There can be a steep learning curve to develop the expertise and organisational skills to use the CRS system effectively but the transformation in the classroom experience for students and lecturers can make this increased effort very worthwhile.

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